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Rediscovering the Naisiusiu Beds type section: new insights from Olduvai Gorge (Tanzania)

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The Naisiusiu Beds (NaB) type section at Olduvai (Oldupai) Gorge, Tanzania, represents a historically significant though still underexplored Late Pleistocene sequence that has recently attracted renewed geological and archaeological attention. Despite its early recognition, the site was overlooked in recent decades, leaving key aspects of its stratigraphy, chronology, and archaeological content poorly resolved. This study presents the results of an integrated multidisciplinary study, combining micromorphology, lithic technology, and palaeontological data within a recently revised stratigraphic and chronological framework. This approach also benefits from the systematic study of historical lithic collections recovered by the Leakeys in 1931 and 1969, combined with new materials retrieved during recent surveys conducted by the THOR (Tanzania Human Origins Research) team.

Micromorphological analyses show that the NaB sequence includes multiple lithofacies reflecting different depositional environments and site formation processes. Radiocarbon dating of ostrich eggshell fragments constrains the lower part of the sequence to >50 ka, while the middle unit is dated to 34.2 ± 2.8 ka, and the upper unit extends into the Last Glacial Maximum. The palaeontological assemblage, although taxonomically limited, is consistent with open grassland-savannah environments and supports the hypothesis of sedimentation within a semi-arid, episodically wetter landscape.

Taken together, our results show that the NaB succession is a robust chronological and archaeological reference sequence documenting multiple phases of hominin behaviour across major environmental transitions from MIS 3 to MIS 2.

Unveiling nature and origin of mesophotic seabed features on a ridge offshore Cape Licosa (Tyrrhenian Sea, Italy)

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The PRIN22 CORSUB Project - To the CORE of the SUBstrate: inception and development of Mediterranean algal reefs aimed at studying an offshore area of Punta Licosa promontory (Tyrrhenian Sea, southern Italy), where enigmatic seabed morphology of unknown nature and origin occurred within mesophotic environments at 75-85 m water depth. To do so, the area was investigated through multibeam bathymetry and backscatter, side-scan sonar, chirp profiling, ROV observations and sampling to assess both their geomorphological origin and possible habitat significance. The studied area included a ridge, tectonic in origin, with a strong asymmetry. The eastern flank was quite steep and tectonically controlled, while the western flank was less steep and it showed a deep sector, below 100 m of water depth, where rocky outcrops occurred whereas the shallow sector included a field of subcircular to polygonal mounded features. Seismic identified the acoustic substratum as an inclined layered unit corresponding to the Miocene Cilento Flysch group as it occurred along the coast. It outcropped in the deep sector of the ridge, whereas it is draped by a thin, discontinuous Holocene sediment cover towards the top. Here, morphometric analysis on digital terrain model, using the CoMMa toolbox identified 565 discrete mounds, averaging 8.6×6.1 m in plan and ~ 0.4 m in relief, with a predominant NE–SE orientation. High-backscatter rings encircle lower-reflectivity cores, producing a regular “beehive-like” seabed texture that enhances small-scale habitat heterogeneity. ROV imagery shows coarse biogenic sediments and localized encrustations of coralline algae and bivalves on rocks, indicating that these mounds provide preferential substrates for benthic colonization. We suggest that such bedforms inherited an irregular paleo-topography from the subaerial erosion of the Miocene rocky substrate during the Last Glacial Maximum. Holocene sedimentation drapes the substrates, including coarse biogenic sediment and rhodolith beds (both actual and fossil) and is sculptured by bottom currents and fostered by biogenic accretion. This interplay of paleo-topography and sediment dynamics generates seabed roughness and sedimentary contrasts, fostering habitat patchiness and structural complexity within the mesophotic zone. These findings underscore how paleo-topographic inheritance and post-glacial sedimentary dynamics influence present-day habitat distribution and complexity on Mediterranean continental shelves.

Neanderthal nasal morphology and function: insights from the Altamura skeleton (Southern Italy)

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The adaptation of Neanderthals to extreme climatic conditions is a topic of significant interest in paleoanthropology. Predictably, researchers have focused extensively on the nasal region, which is also particularly distinctive in *Homo neanderthalensis*. Nevertheless, studies have been limited by the scarcity of preserved bony nasal structures - especially the internal ones - in the human fossil record. Recently, we presented a study on the complete inner nasal structures of an early Neanderthal skeleton from Altamura, southern Italy. This exceptional specimen was discovered in October 1993 during a speleological survey of a newly identified karst system northeast of Altamura in the Apulia region. The nearly complete skeleton is situated within a niche in a very small chamber of the karstic system, covered with characteristic concretions and coatings of varying thickness, which are among the reasons that continue to hinder the removal of the fossil from the cave and require only on-site analyses. The extraordinary state of preservation of the specimen enabled the study of structures absent from the entire human fossil record, such as those of the nasal cavity, providing previously unavailable evidence for both this species and the human fossil record. It also contributed to resolving a longstanding debate over certain inner nasal traits proposed as Neanderthal autapomorphies in relation to cold climates. With these premises, we reconstructed a 3D model of the nasal cavity from this specimen and compared it with available samples, namely those from modern human populations from various geographic regions, each characterized by distinct climatic adaptations of the nose. Our observations point to an indirect influence of climatic adaptations on the Neanderthal midface. They also suggest that, compared to modern humans, Neanderthals relied on a different functional model, based on their archaic facial morphology. Our observations ultimately call for accounting for organisms' energetic demands when studying their morphology.

Geomorphological-paleoenvironmental coastal evolution and vertical motions in a volcanic setting: the Campania Plain (southern Italy) case study

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The post-Miocene back-arc extension of the Southern Apennines and the Tyrrhenian Sea drove the formation of Early Pleistocene basins. As one of the largest coastal basins on the Tyrrhenian margin, the Campania Plain features a 3 km-thick Quaternary infill, consisting of a complex alternation of marine, alluvial, and volcanic sequences. The Campania Plain has seen intense volcanism since ~2 Ma, with active centres like Vesuvius, Ischia and Campi Flegrei concentrated in its southern part. Vertical motions along the basin's inner margin are documented by raised marine terraces and associated deposits outcropping along the Mt. Fellino ridge, and by the analysis of deep boreholes. In this work, a c. 80-m-deep core has been characterized in detail, and newly acquired chronological data provide insight into the depositional evolution and tectonic dynamics of the Campania Plain's interior throughout the Late Quaternary. The chronological constraints include both numerical dating (⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar and amino acid racemisation on ostracods) and relative dating through tephrostratigraphic correlations, which allow identification of the stratigraphic record of MIS 7 and MIS 5e sea-level highstands.

The multidisciplinary surface and shallow subsurface morphostratigraphic work provides new constraints on the interaction between sea-level fluctuations, pyroclastic aggradation, and subsidence, as well as on associated differential vertical motions in the Late Quaternary Campania Plain basin.

Il ruolo della variabilità climatica nella transizione Paleolitico Medio - Superiore nel Sud Italia: nuove evidenze dalla Puglia

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Il sud Italia rappresenta una delle aree principali per indagare la scomparsa dei Neanderthal e la progressiva diffusione dell'Anatomically Modern Human (AMH) durante la transizione tra Paleolitico Medio e Superiore (~ 50 e 40 ka). La variabilità climatica e ambientale tipica del MIS 3, caratterizzata da cicli Dansgaard-Oeschger ed eventi di Heinrich (HE), può aver fortemente influenzato la distribuzione di queste popolazioni, contribuendo alla progressiva scomparsa dei Neanderthal. In questo studio, presentiamo nuovi dati isotopici ottenuti da due stalagmiti, SA1 e SA201, provenienti dalla Grotta di Sant'Angelo (Puglia) con l'obiettivo di fornire nuove informazioni paleoclimatiche per l'area. La crescita di entrambi i campioni inizia durante l'Heinrich Event 5 (HE5 49-47 ka) e prosegue fino all'Olocene con una deposizione quasi continua. L'unica interruzione - o fase di crescita estremamente lenta - si colloca durante la transizione tra GI e GS 12 (in dettaglio $47.4 \pm 0.3 - 43.16 \pm 0.28$ ka in SA1 e $45.72 \pm 0.19 - 43.41 \pm 0.15$ ka per SA201). I valori $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ riflettono principalmente la variazione nella quantità e provenienza delle precipitazioni, mentre i $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ indicano cambiamenti nell'attività microbica del suolo, e nella densità e tipologia di vegetazione. In corrispondenza dello hiatus, si osserva una diminuzione delle precipitazioni anche nella Grotta di Pozzo Cucù e una progressiva apertura della vegetazione, come suggerito da record pollinici dell'area. Questa fase di apparente deterioramento climatico si colloca tra gli Heinrich Events 5 e 4 (HE4 40.2-38.3 ka), entrambi riconoscibili nei record di Sant'Angelo come periodi meno favorevoli, caratterizzati da diminuzione delle precipitazioni e ridotta attività del suolo, sebbene non così marcati come nei record provenienti dal Mediterraneo occidentale. In conclusione, al momento i record pugliesi non mostrano evidenze di singoli eventi climatici particolarmente estremi tali da sostenere una possibile estinzione. Tuttavia, è necessario approfondire lo scenario in cui una sequenza di fasi di stress climatico e ambientale moderate ma ravvicinate – distribuite in un intervallo di ~ 8 ka - possano aver avuto un impatto significativo sul territorio e sulla distribuzione delle popolazioni coinvolte.

The last million years of eastern African evolution as told at Olduvai Gorge (Tanzania):

State-of-the-art and research perspectives

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Olduvai (Oldupai) Gorge (northern Tanzania) is one of the most significant paleontological and archaeological sites in Africa –and in the world. It is located within a UNESCO Global Geopark (Ngorongoro Lengai) and a UNESCO World Heritage Site (Ngorongoro Conservation Area). The exceptionally rich assemblages of fossils and stone tools preserved –with near continuity– within the Olduvai stratigraphic succession testify to the eastern African ecosystem change over the past 2 Ma, as well as to key transitions in human evolution. Although scholars from several countries have been studying the site widely for over a century, most research focused on the lower terms of the succession (i.e., Beds I-III, yielding evidence of early hominin species such as *Paranthropus boisei*, *Homo habilis*, and *Homo ergaster*). In contrast, recent efforts of the Tanzania Human Origins Research (THOR) project are investigating the middle-to-upper part of the succession. The purpose of these studies is to reconstruct the latest Early Pleistocene to present-day palaeoenvironmental conditions and their change, as well as the ecological impact of hominins. The analyzed stratigraphic units –i.e. Bed IV, Masek Beds, Ndotu Beds, and Naisiusiu Beds– are one of the few datable open-air geological successions spanning the last million years in eastern Africa. Consequently, they are particularly significant for investigating some of the major milestones in human evolution. These include the spread of *Homo sapiens*, and the Early-Middle Stone Age and Middle-Later Stone Age transitions, as well as large-scale palaeoenvironmental events like the Early-Middle Pleistocene Transition.

Ricostruzioni paleoclimatiche tardo quaternarie da speleotemi sardi: stato dell'arte e prospettive future

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La Sardegna, per la sua posizione, è fondamentale nello studio del paleoclima mediterraneo. La mancanza di depositi lacustri pre-olocenici rende indispensabile l'utilizzo di speleotemi come archivi naturali per la ricostruzione paleoclimatica tramite proxy-data a scala deca-millenaria. Le oltre 3000 grotte presenti nell'isola consentono di raccogliere campioni da vari contesti e periodi di crescita.

Recentemente, un notevole sforzo è stato effettuato per l'analisi del MIS7 (Columbu et al., 2019), MIS5 (Columbu et al., 2017; 2019) e Olocene (Columbu et al., 2024) tramite serie temporali di $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, elementi in traccia, tasso di crescita e petrografia degli speleotemi dalle grotte del Bue Marino, Crovassa Azzurra e Suttaterra de Sarpis. Sono in corso di studio l'evento 4.2 (Columbu et al., submitted) e gli ultimi ca. 100 mila anni (Colmanet et al., in prep.) dalle grotte de S'Armidda e Su Pertusu rispettivamente.

L'intervento presenta una panoramica sulle attuali conoscenze paleoclimatiche relative al tardo Quaternario, basate sull'analisi dei speleotemi sardi, e ne evidenzia il rapporto con il contesto mediterraneo. Si illustreranno anche possibili sviluppi futuri. Inoltre, viene approfondito il ruolo del clima sulle dinamiche ed evoluzioni culturali-demografiche delle antiche civiltà sarde, concentrandosi in particolare su due aspetti: 1) il popolamento dell'isola e 2) il periodo nuragico.

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A Shelf-Confined, Underfed Depositional Model: Insights from the Late Quaternary of Western Sardinia margin

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A review of morphostratigraphic investigations conducted over the last decade on the Late Quaternary depositional system of the Gulf of Oristano and the continental shelf of western Sardinia is presented. The continental shelf along the western Sardinian margin is characterized as an underfed system, marked by limited terrigenous sediment supply and significant biogenic carbonate production. Quaternary depositional systems are strongly influenced by the tectonic framework of the margin, including the presence of intra-shelf sedimentary basins and structural highs.

During Pleistocene transgressive and regressive cycles, the central shelf sector was primarily supplied by the Tirso River, with a secondary contribution from rivers draining the Arburese region. The shelf edge, located at approximately 200 m depth, remained unexposed during recent Pleistocene sea-level lowstands, confining the entire depositional system within the shelf.

An extensive dataset, including geophysical (morphobathymetry, acoustic backscatter, and high- to ultra-high-resolution seismic data) and sedimentological analyses, reveals that: (i) no deltaic system developed in the deeper sector during the Last Glacial Maximum, despite fluvial sediment input, due to the combined effects of low sediment supply, hydrodynamic conditions and paleotopography; (ii) a series of backstepping depositional terraces and overstepping cemented barriers formed in response to variations in sea-level rise rates between 13 and 8 ka; (iii) the incised valley of the Tirso River was filled with estuarine sediments within the more sheltered sector of the Gulf of Oristano between 9 and 6 ka; and (iv) shoreline progradation led to the formation of the present coastal system between 6 and 2 ka.

These findings outline a depositional model typical of a shelf-confined, underfed morpho-sedimentary system, strongly controlled by tectonics and hydrodynamics, which departs from standard sequence stratigraphy models.

Crisi, rifugi e adattamenti: dinamiche neandertaliane durante il MIS 4 in Europa

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Il Marine Isotope Stage 4 (MIS 4; ca. 71–57 ka) rappresenta una fase di profonda riorganizzazione nelle dinamiche ecologiche, demografiche e culturali delle popolazioni neandertaliane europee. In un contesto di marcato deterioramento climatico e ambientale, recenti evidenze paleogenetiche indicano un significativo collo di bottiglia intorno a ~65 ka, associato al depopolamento di ampie porzioni dell'Europa centro-settentrionale ed orientale e alla persistenza di aree rifugio nell'Europa sud-occidentale. Tuttavia, l'identificazione di tali rifugi resta problematica, essendo fortemente influenzata da bias di ricerca e dinamiche tafonomiche. Il MIS 4 si configura anche come un momento chiave di trasformazione tecno-comportamentale. Si osserva una riduzione della variabilità tecnologica e l'emergere di strategie adattative specifiche, tra cui una maggiore mobilità stagionale e lo sviluppo di sistemi tecnici portatili e versatili. In questo quadro, il tecno-complesso Quina assume un ruolo centrale: ampiamente attestato, seppur con variabilità regionale, nella Francia sud-occidentale, nella Penisola Iberica e nell'Italia sudalpina, può essere interpretato come un marker comportamentale legato a condizioni ambientali severe. Nell'Italia sudalpina, l'integrazione di analisi multi-scalari (tecnologiche, economiche, paleoecologiche e stagionali) con nuove evidenze cronologiche e paleoambientali da contesti chiave, quali Grotta de Nadale, Grotta di Fumane e Grotta della Ghiacciaia, rafforza l'ipotesi di una diffusa riorganizzazione adattativa. A questa fase segue, nel MIS 3, un processo di ricolonizzazione delle aree precedentemente abbandonate, accompagnato da una rinnovata diversificazione delle strategie tecniche. Nonostante la ridotta variabilità genetica ereditata dal MIS 4, i processi di riadattamento locale e interazione tra gruppi contribuiscono alla formazione di un mosaico bio-culturale articolato. Il MIS 4 emerge quindi come una soglia critica nella storia evolutiva dei Neandertal, in cui stress ambientali, contrazione demografica e innovazione tecnologica si intrecciano, offrendo una chiave interpretativa per comprenderne la resilienza nel contesto delle dinamiche quaternarie.

Paleogeographic evolution of the Po Plain at the Last Glacial – present interglacial transition

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The Po Plain hosts a thick sedimentary succession with high preservation potential due to high subsidence rates. The Po River, the trunk river, flows from the Western Alps to the Adriatic Sea and receives sedimentary inputs from South Alpine and Apennine tributaries. Lithological differences between the Alpine and Apennine drainage areas are reflected in the composition of sediments delivered by major rivers and accumulated in the Po Basin since the Pleistocene, making this site particularly suitable for provenance analysis.

In this study we reconstructed the evolution of the fluvial network of the central-eastern Po Plain at the transition from the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) to the present interglacial, through integrated stratigraphic–compositional analysis. Stratigraphic architecture was reconstructed based on the correlation of cores, water wells and cone penetration tests in a dense grid of cross-sections, constrained by tens of radiocarbon ages. Within this framework, petrographic and geochemical analyses were performed on core samples to constrain sediment provenance.

Three main chronostratigraphic intervals were identified, allowing the reconstruction of three different paleogeographic scenarios. Between ~29 and 20 ka, deposition was dominated by the Po River which migrated along a ~20 km-wide channel belt. This phase records high sediment supply, largely fed by Alpine fluvioglacial systems active during the LGM.

The phase between ~20 and 16 ka is characterized by narrower Po channel belts, with higher preservation of floodplain muds, and by a northward expansion of the Apennine delivery system. This phase reflects reduced sediment delivery to the basin due to the deactivation of fluvioglacial systems and the formation of large South Alpine lakes acting as sediment traps.

The third phase, from ~14 to 10 ka, records channel incision and the development of incipient paleosols in the interfluves. Fluvial incision was driven by rapid glacier melt and increased river discharge during the Bølling–Allerød. Fluvial activity remained mostly confined within river incisions until the Early Holocene when the area entered in the backwater influence during the last phases of post-glacial sea-level rise.

Paleoenvironmental reconstruction from unconventional sedimentary archives: The *matte* of *Posidonia oceanica* from the western Nora bay (Sardinia)

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Coastal areas contain key sediment archives that can provide major insights into the millennial environmental changes. In the Mediterranean region, such modifications are controlled by both climatic processes and human impact, notably in the late Holocene (e.g., last 4.0 ka). Here we reconstructed the evolution of the vegetational landscape and its interrelationship to human activity in the coastal southern Sardinian site of Ancient Nora through the pollen analysis of *Posidonia oceanica* matte sediment core, the first study of its kind to use this pioneering material in the Central Mediterranean.

The city of Nora holds significant historical importance as a port city and center for cultural and material exchange for the various cultural groups that occupied the area over time, though little is known about how the coastal environment evolved as these groups interacted with their environment. With this aim, we extracted a core from the large *P. oceanica* meadow which outcrops in the large and sheltered bay west of the town.

The pollen analysis, corroborated by a new suite of radiocarbon dates, allowed to describe both the changes in vegetation and the evolution of land-use at Nora from the 9th century BCE until the end of the 2nd century CE. Pollen analysis detects both regional maquis vegetation and local wetland/coastal landscape and confirms the historical and archaeological evidence of an increasing human activity linked to Ancient Nora's development. Human impact intensifies with Phoenician presence in the 8th century BCE, marked by declining arboreal taxa and rising anthropogenic indicators such as *Olea*, *Myrtus*, and *Vitis*. During the Punic period (4th century BCE), evidence shows progressive land use and cereal cultivation, consistent with grain exports to Carthage. In the Roman period (from the 3rd century BCE), the landscape becomes more open, with minimal forest cover and increased *Olea* and *Pinus*, reflecting urbanization and expansion. The study also considers natural environmental influences and demonstrates the value of *P. oceanica* matte sediments for palynological research, offering insights into land use and vegetation change over time.

New geoarchaeological data from Landro Cave (NE Italy). Preliminary results of BOS Project (PARQ 2025)

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The Cansiglio plateau (Northeastern Italy) is a pre-Alpine carbonatic massif well known for its prehistoric record. Since the 1990s, numerous Late Palaeolithic and Mesolithic sites have been discovered and excavated by the University of Ferrara. These include a few open-air hunting stands located throughout the large Piancansiglio polje and an intra-morainic bog site (Palughetto), which serves as the regional reference for reconstructing Lateglacial reforestation processes.

In 2017, a new archaeological deposit was identified within a dolina at 1060 m a.s.l. on the northern edge of the Cansiglio. The site, named Landro, is the first cave site in the region and the first multilayered deposit of the plateau. The ongoing archaeological investigations have brought to light a two-metres-thick archaeological sequence spanning from the Early Lateglacial to the Pleistocene-Holocene boundary, with no major erosional events. From a cultural perspective, all the main occupational phases have been attributed to the Late Epigravettian, with the earliest directly dated to the First Part of the Lateglacial. These data, coupled with the Landro Cave's altitude and geographic location, make it a key site for reconstructing the recolonisation of the Alpine area after the LGM.

This paper presents preliminary results and outlines future steps of the ongoing geoarchaeological study of Landro Cave, conducted within the framework of BOS (Beyond Open-air Sites) project, funded by AIQUA PARQ 2025 award.

In particular, the entire stratigraphical sequence will be presented, along with the full set of radiocarbon dates obtained on the main units of interest, as well as the preliminary reconstruction of formation processes and their paleoenvironmental significance, inferred from stratigraphical, micromorphological, and sedimentological data.

Composite marine terrace as indicators of sea-level fluctuations and differential uplift in tectonically segmented continental margin: insights from southern Sardinia (Mediterranean Sea)

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Quaternary marine terraces provide key archives for reconstructing the interplay between sea-level change and tectonic processes along active coastal margins. However, the extent to which terrace stacking patterns reflect eustatic forcing versus uniform/variable uplift remains difficult to assess. In this study, we investigate the Middle-late Pleistocene sedimentary sequence on three sites along the south Sardinia coast. Five unconformity-bounded units are identified and correlated with MIS7, MIS5e and MIS5c highstands documenting repeated phases of marine transgression, shallow-marine system progradation, and regression. The three study areas display contrasting stacking patterns, including composite marine terrace sequences, with superposition of multiple highstand deposits separated by erosional surfaces or a single marine terrace unit.

The elevations of MIS7 and MIS5c shallow-marine units relative to present sea level deviate significantly from global eustatic benchmarks, with mismatches of up to 15–20 m that cannot be explained by glacio-eustatic fluctuations or Mediterranean-scale glacio-isostatic adjustment alone. Instead, the data point to a dominant tectonic control. We propose a model in which southern Sardinia is segmented into distinct crustal blocks experiencing spatially and temporally variable uplift since at least the Pleistocene. The distribution of marine terrace sequences further suggests differential vertical motions and a possible eastward migration of uplift across the south Sardinia.

These findings demonstrate that composite marine terraces represent a key stratigraphic expression of the interaction between tectonics and sea-level fluctuations. More broadly, this study highlights that even in regions characterised by relatively low but variable uplift rates, tectonic segmentation can significantly influence coastal stratigraphy, promoting re-occupation processes and the development of composite marine terrace sequences rather than a staircase of single terraces. Composite marine terraces thus provide a robust framework for identifying subtle tectonic signals in continental margins often regarded as stable or slowly uplifting.

Post Excavation Stratigraphy at Artofago Cave (Tuscany, Italy): crossing technological and spatial data to unravel occupation phases

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Field stratigraphy, based on sedimentological and topographic markers, provides the essential framework for archaeological excavation, yet human occupation phases do not always align with sedimentary boundaries. Multiple cultural horizons may be embedded within a single geological layer, and a single occupation may span several strata. Here we address this challenge through a case study at Artofago Cave in southern Tuscany (Italy), a Late Upper Pleistocene cave site, where field observations alone proved insufficient to resolve the internal sequence of a multi-layered deposit.

We combined spatial coordinates of lithic artefacts with a comprehensive technological database of discrete and metric variables recorded on blanks and cores, applying multivariate statistical modelling to examine the vertical distribution of multiple technological attributes across the stratigraphic sequence.

Our results identify a consistent technological discontinuity within a single sedimentary unit (Layer 2) that does not coincide with any previously recognised sedimentological contact. The discontinuity is marked by a convergent shift in several independent lithic attributes, reflecting a change in core reduction strategies and in the intended products of the knapping sequence.

We argue that post-excavation integration of high-resolution spatial and technological data can reveal occupational shifts invisible to field observation alone, offering a replicable method to refine stratigraphic subdivisions independently of sedimentological criteria. Future integration with sediment micromorphology will further test the archaeological significance of these technological horizons and their relationship with depositional processes.

Da bacino torboso tardo quaternario a serbatoio idroelettrico: un secolo di trasformazioni antropiche al Lago di Campotosto (Appennino centrale, Italia)

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Il Lago di Campotosto è un bacino artificiale di alta quota situato nell'Appennino centrale. Esso fu realizzato su una preesistente depressione umida e torbosa formatosi nel Tardo Quaternario, in parte sfruttata già nei primi decenni del Novecento e successivamente inserita in un più ampio sistema idroelettrico attraverso un complesso assetto di tre sbarramenti e importanti opere di derivazione. In questo studio utilizziamo cartografia storica e dati d'archivio, fotografie aeree del 1945 e del 1954, ortofoto e immagini satellitari multitemporali, insieme a rilievi geomorfologici di terreno e da drone condotti durante fasi di basso livello idrico, per ricostruire l'assetto pre-invaso del bacino torboso e seguire il modo in cui l'uso umano e la regolazione artificiale ne hanno rimodellato forme e processi nell'ultimo secolo.

La cartografia geomorfologica multitemporale mostra una progressiva obliterazione della morfologia naturale della torbiera, inizialmente legata alle attività di escavazione della torba e alle opere di drenaggio, e successivamente alla sommersione e al parziale rimaneggiamento connessi alla costruzione del serbatoio e alle prime fasi di allagamento nella metà del XX secolo. Le successive oscillazioni del livello del lago hanno poi determinato l'instaurarsi di una drawdown zone attiva, caratterizzata da esposizione intermittente di superfici sommerse, alterazione dei depositi torbosi, riattivazione di vie di drenaggio, erosione di sponda e incisione di gullies, nonché da locali fenomeni di instabilità delle rive. Anche la rete idrografica risponde a queste variazioni del livello di base attraverso migrazione degli sbocchi, riorganizzazione delle foci e aggiustamenti di breve termine dei canali. In questa prospettiva, la ricostruzione diacronica e storica fornisce una baseline antropogenica utile a interpretare le interazioni tra uomo e ambiente attraverso il mutare dell'uso delle risorse naturali, documentando il passaggio dallo sfruttamento della torba alla produzione di energia idroelettrica e il relativo imprint geomorfologico antropico su forme ereditate in un paesaggio montano regolato dell'Appennino centrale.

British hyenas of the late Early to early Middle Pleistocene

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Hyenas (Carnivora, Hyaenidae) are a taxonomic group of remarkable relevance for many aspects of Quaternary research. During the Pleistocene (as today), most hyenas were “bone-crackers”, representing a severe reduction of the different “ecomorphs” once existing and documented by a rich fossil record. Yet, the habit of consuming carrion, cracking open and ingesting bones, which earned hyenas a bad reputation in folk and mass culture, is as precious as unique for studies from systematic paleontology to taphonomy, as the feeding behavior of bone-cracking hyenas often causes them to be bone collectors. This is also important from a historical perspective. For example, the understanding that hyenas once inhabited caves in Europe, and accumulated bones within them, was a powerful realization that changed the way of looking at Pleistocene deposits since the early nineteenth century. Moreover, during the Pleistocene, hominins were one of the few groups other than hyenas capable of processing bones to access their nutrient-rich content, fueling discussion on the direct or indirect *Homo*-hyaenid interactions. In striking contrast with the Late Pleistocene mass occurrences of “cave” hyenas, the late Early and Middle Pleistocene fossil record of the groups is rather patchy in England. Two species, *Pachycrocuta brevirostris* and *Crocuta crocuta* (or *C. spelea*) have been reported from Bacton, Corton, Mundesley, Overstrand, Pakefield, Palling, Sidestrand, Westbury, and West Runton. Here, a revision of these findings is presented, clarifying their taxonomic attribution and discussing biochronological and paleobiological implications. British hyenas of the late Early to early Middle Pleistocene are mainly represented by isolated and/or fragmentary findings, although some remarkable specimens are present. Westbury-sub-Mendip is the only site in Europe where remains of *P. brevirostris* and *C. crocuta* are both present and were recovered from a firm stratigraphic context, documenting a substitution of the two species along the stratigraphic sequence and hence supporting the biochronological relevance of the *Pachycrocuta*-*Crocuta* replacement.

A spotted hyena (*Crocuta crocuta*) from Pirro III (Pirro Nord, Apricena, southern Italy)

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The discovery of palaeontological remains at Pirro Nord occurred in 1969, with three systematic excavation campaigns and several surveys carried out in the immediately following years (1969–1971). Although the locality was extensively investigated over the years and especially after the discovery of lithic tools in the 2000s, most of the Pleistocene material collected in the initial campaigns has not been the subject of dedicated studies, and it is currently under examination after the rediscovery of the so-called “Dagostino Collection” in Bari (Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra e Geoambientali). During this revision, we identified a hyena mandible, from a site labelled Pirro III, that does not belong to the giant hyena *Pachycrocuta brevirostris*, the only hyena previously known from Pirro Nord, but to *Crocuta crocuta*. The small size and dental proportions of the Pirro III spotted hyena best fit with the Middle Pleistocene *Crocuta*, thus suggesting a consistent age for Pirro III. Furthermore, the *Pachycrocuta-Crocuta* replacement occurred, in Europe, ~0.8 Ma, indicating that Pirro III is close to or younger than this age. Moreover, the attached sediment and the color appearance of the fossil of Pirro III differ from that typical of the other finds from Pirro Nord. The presence of *C. crocuta* at Pirro III indicates that deposits younger than those yielding the typical fauna of Pirro Nord (generally considered ~1.6–1.3 Ma) were present in the locality.

Late Quaternary coastal evolution and paleoclimate variability in the Baratti Gulf (Tuscany, Italy)

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The Gulf of Baratti (Tuscany) hosts a 10 meters thick sedimentary succession representing the classic coastal Quaternary of Tuscany. This sequence provides significant evidence of the transition from a marine to a continental environment.

In a relatively narrow bay such as Baratti, the presence of heterogeneous facies (beaches, dunes, sheet floods and soils) reflects a local sensitivity to eustatic and climatic variations. The use of luminescence dating allows for a more precise definition of the transitions between the different sedimentary environments, placing them within the broader context of Quaternary global climate dynamics.

The sequence comprises a single marine terrace, extending from basal transgressive lag to foreshore facies. Above this, coastal dunes are intercalated with reddened paleosol levels. In the upper succession, the dunes are intensely bioturbated and interrupted by coarse-grained sheetflood deposits, evidencing episodic flows in an ephemeral fluvial system. A paleosol separates these from an overlying meandering river point-bar deposit, capped by modern soil.

Luminescence ages constrain the marine terrace to late Marine Isotopic Stage 5 (97 ± 8 ka), sheetflood deposits and associate paleosol to MIS 3 (41 ± 3 ka and 36 ± 4 ka), point-bar deposits to late MIS 3 (29 ± 2 ka).

This reveals a single marine body (MIS 5), followed by continental deposits spanning MIS 3–2 and early Holocene phases. Ephemeral rivers during the mild MIS 3 interstadial, alternating with paleosols, highlight high-frequency wet/dry fluctuations, while late MIS 3 meandering reflects a wetter climate in Tuscany.

The Roman Climatic Optimum: a review of Mediterranean marine fossil archives

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Climate variability reflects the interactions between natural forcing (changes in solar irradiance, volcanic eruptions and environmental feedbacks) and external forcing and has an important influence on the socio-economic development, ecological systems and human issues.

In this framework, the Roman Period has particularly interested scientists, primarily due to the interaction between climate and history. It's well-known that during the Roman Period, there was a climatic optimum aptly named the "Roman Climatic Optimum (RCO)," which certainly may have influenced the events that unfolded during those years. The RCO represents a phase of relatively warm and climatically stable conditions that broadly spans from approximately 100 BCE to 500 CE. This interval coincides with the expansion and consolidation of the Roman Republic and Empire and has attracted increasing attention as a potential example of climate–society interactions in antiquity. This work aims to provide a review of the climate and environmental changes documented in marine fossil archives available and relevant to the Roman period in the Mediterranean region. Through the analysis of multiple proxies (paleotemperatures, planktonic foraminifera, calcareous nannofossils and geochemical indicators) comes from several sites of the Mediterranean Sea, a coherent picture emerges of widespread warming during the Roman period with relatively high temperatures and reduced climate variability compared to subsequent phases. These favourable climatic conditions appear to have supported agricultural development, population growth, and the socio-economic stability of the Roman Empire.

The planktonic foraminifera and calcareous nannofossils also indicate an increase in marine productivity, likely linked both to more humid climatic conditions and to intensified human activities, such as land use and water management. In this sense, the RCO represents one of the earliest examples in which a significant interaction between climate and human impact on marine ecosystems can be observed. Toward the end of the period, reconstructions show a gradual cooling trend, associated with environmental and historical instability that culminated in the decline of the Empire. Overall, the study highlights the importance of marine archives in understanding past climate dynamics and their relationship with human societies, providing valuable insights for interpreting current climate challenges.

New tephrochronological constraints for technocomplexes' transitions at *Grotta di Castelcivita*, Cilento (Italy)

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Grotta di Castelcivita (Cilento, southern Italy) archives a rich Middle-Upper Palaeolithic archaeological sequence including the Mousterian, Uluzzian, and Aurignacian (Proto and Early) technocomplexes. The sequence is temporally constrained by ¹⁴C and OSL dating, which yielded ages between 48.6 and 40 ka, and is topped by deposits of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI), ⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar dated at 40.01 ± 0.14 ka. Other numerous tephra (i.e., volcanic ash) layers underly the CI deposits, some of which are located close to the Mousterian-Uluzzian, the Uluzzian-Protoaurignacian, and the Protoaurignacian-Early Aurignacian boundaries but have never been studied before. These tephra layers could be potentially correlated with other dated eruptions and thus provide a good opportunity to further constraint the chronology of the Castelcivita Palaeolithic record. In this study, we present glass geochemical analyses of five newly investigated tephra layers from Castelcivita. The obtained glass geochemistry composition indicate that all Castelcivita tephra layers sourced from Campi Flegrei caldera and allows reliable correlations with eruptive units from the near-vent succession of Acquamorta (Monti di Procida, Campania). Further correlations were determined with tephra layers from the lake sediments of Fucino basin and Lago Grande di Monticchio, allowing us to temporally constrain the whole Castelcivita sequence between ~40 and 55 ka and to refine the chronology of the technocomplex boundaries. In particular, the end of the Mousterian, and hence the terminus post quem of the overlaying Uluzzian, and the Uluzzian-Protoaurignacian boundary, previously dated at ~44-43 ka and ~41.5-40.5 ka, respectively, can be now precisely dated at 45.4 ± 1.0 ka and 42.01 ± 0.35 ka. Furthermore, the middle part of the excavated Mousterian occupation can now be dated at 54.8 ± 2.2 ka, whilst the transition from Proto- to Early Aurignacian can be constrained between 42.01 ± 0.35 ka and ~40.6 ka. Finally, the occurrence of equivalent tephra layers in the Lago Grande di Monticchio and Grotta Riparo of Uluzzo-C successions, allows synchronizing the Castelcivita record with this regional pollen series, enabling us to also evaluate the paleoclimatic and paleoenvironmental setting of the human occupation and cultural transitions at this site for these crucial cultural layers and transitions.

How much luminescence may contribute to solve late Quaternary high frequency millennial scale climate fluctuations?

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Luminescence dating provides a critical, though coarse, chronological backbone for high-frequency millennial-scale climate events. Its main contribution is offering the only absolute dating method for terrestrial sediments (loess, dunes) beyond the range of radiocarbon (i.e., beyond ~50,000 years). However, because typical age uncertainties are $\pm 5\text{--}10\%$ (e.g., $\pm 2,000$ years at 40 ka), luminescence cannot resolve the decadal-to-centennial leads, lags, or durations that define "high-frequency" fluctuations. Instead, it solves the broader problem of synchronizing the presence of abrupt events across different continents, providing essential temporal context where no other method works.

An example is given by the study of Marine Isotope Stage 3 (MIS 3), spanning from 60 to 27 ka. This stage was a relatively cold interglacial characterized by extreme climate instability, punctuated by rapid and high-frequency warm and cold fluctuations. These include at least six colder Heinrich (H) events and fourteen warmer Dansgaard–Oeschger (DO) events. These fluctuations are primarily documented through Greenland ice cores and have been attributed to Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) variability. The terrestrial paleoclimate record of MIS 3 lacks sufficient resolution compared to ice core data. Hiatuses and the scarcity of continuous records of environmental changes in continental profiles make direct comparison impossible. To better constrain MIS 3 events, a detailed study was conducted in Lanzarote (Canary Islands, Atlantic Ocean), Sardinia (central Mediterranean Sea island), and Tuscany (central Italy, western Mediterranean Sea). In these sites, the MIS 3 terrestrial successions are comparable and were investigated in terms of sedimentology to define paleoenvironments, and dated using luminescence, integrated where possible with radiocarbon (^{14}C) ages. Luminescence dating has provided a critical framework for correlating Late Quaternary humid phases across the western Mediterranean. In Lanzarote, a debris flow-dominated alluvial fan system indicates a first heavy rainfall phase at ~50–38 ka, followed by channelized deposits suggesting a second pluvial interval at ~37–22 ka. In NW Sardinia, a comparable chronology is recorded, with debris flows reflecting intense rainfall at ~50–36 ka, succeeded by sheet flood and shallow channel facies associated with sustained rainfall at ~36–27 ka. In Tuscany, a braided stream system attests to strong rainfall influence at ~44 ka, whereas a meandering stream phase indicates renewed humid conditions at ~29 ka. Despite luminescence age uncertainties, the consistency of these depositional episodes across a longitudinal transect from the Atlantic to the central Mediterranean

suggests a regional-scale climatic control on millennial-scale humid events during MIS 3 and, possibly, into early Stage of MIS 2. These results demonstrate that luminescence chronologies, while not resolving sub-centennial variability, are essential for correlating high-frequency rainfall-driven depositional events across distinct Mediterranean sectors. This study confirms that MIS 3 is undoubtedly a key analogue for abrupt climate changes, highlighting the fragility of ice-ocean-atmosphere systems. Understanding its dynamics and constraining the age of these events in the terrestrial domain will help assess future risks, such as AMOC collapse or rapid warming events.

Mid-Late Holocene vegetation history and human impact in the south-eastern Alps: a multi-proxy palaeoenvironmental record from Lake Caldonazzo (Trentino, Italy)

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This study presents a high-resolution multi-proxy palaeoenvironmental reconstruction from the sedimentary record of Lake Caldonazzo (south-eastern Trentino), spanning from the 6th to 1st millennium BCE. By integrating bio- and geochemical proxies (micro-botanical data, micro-charcoal, faecal biomarkers, and trace elements) we reconstruct the interplay between environmental dynamics and anthropogenic impacts from the Neolithic to the Early Iron Age. During the Middle Holocene, the Valsugana landscape supported stable, predominantly pristine silver fir and beech forests. Despite the absence of known Neolithic settlements, open-land indicators and low-intensity pastoral signals suggest intermittent human exploitation of this resource-rich environment. From the late 4th millennium BCE, a progressive decline in forest cover reflects the synergistic effects of climate cooling, associated with the waning of the Holocene Thermal Maximum, and expansion of agropastoral economies typical of the Copper Age.

The subsequent Early and Middle Bronze Age record documents accelerated deforestation coupled with the expansion of pastoralism and cereal cultivation, intensifying anthropogenic pressure (as marked by increased faecal biomarker values) and an early, stepwise rise in metal enrichment factors, which may signal the onset of local metallurgy as early as the Middle Bronze Age. The Recent–Final Bronze Age marks the peak of human impact in the Valsugana. Arboreal pollen declines sharply as open herbaceous taxa expand, while rising *Glomus* spores point to accelerating soil erosion and sustained elevated faecal biomarker values reflect intense demographic pressure. Micro-charcoal reveals both distant smelting activity and sustained local burning, converging with a pronounced Cu enrichment factor peak around 1280 BCE, confirming large-scale smelting activity. This evidence supports south-eastern Trentino's role as a continental-scale copper production hub, documented archaeologically by over 200 smelting sites in the Valsugana area. A declining Cu enrichment factor from the mid-12th century BCE points to a progressive reduction in smelting activity, likely driven by resource depletion, ecological degradation, and socio-political reorganisation. Forest recovery was rapid once anthropogenic pressure subsided, with fir and beech recolonising high-altitude areas from the mid-11th century BCE.

Reconstructing long-term natural resources management in the Salut and Bisya oases (Central Sultanate of Oman)

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This study investigates the long-term exploitation of natural resources in a semi-arid alluvial plain of the central Sultanate of Oman that today host the Salut and Bisya oasis; our focus is on the reconstruction of land use changes and water management from the late prehistory to the present. The resource management evolution is reconstructed through the mapping of natural and anthropogenic geomorphological features related to soil and water use. The methodological framework integrates remote sensing data, high-resolution DTMs derived from UAV photogrammetry, and field surveys. A twofold spatial approach is adopted: at the regional scale (1:40.000), geomorphological mapping defines the environmental framework, while at the local scale (1:2.200), high-resolution mapping focuses on landesque features within the core of Bronze Age to Medieval oasis. Anthropogenic features, including falaj irrigation systems, agricultural mounds and abandoned field partitioning have been identified through satellite imagery, UAV data, and field surveys.

In the Bronze age, the oasis was larger than it is today and progressively shrank to its more recent configuration, consisting of patches of green cultivations with a wide desert landscape. We propose to classify oasis patches using a fresh approach, applicable to other arid environments, based on their state of use (active, recently abandoned, fossil), as inferred from palm groves distribution and the state of preservation of cultivation features and irrigation facilities. The spatial distribution and condition of these features allow the identification of patterns of oasis expansion, contraction, and/or relocation. Results show how the management of water and soil resources is key to the survival of oases in arid contexts since the late antiquity. The resulting maps reveals multiple phases of adaptation to progressive aridification over the last ca. 3500 years. In particular, the introduction and development of the falaj systems and the reconstructed size of cultivated areas reflect shifts in water availability and resource management strategies aimed at facing ongoing climate changes. This research provides new insights into the resilience of oasis agricultural systems in arid environments and offers a framework for understanding long-term human and environment interactions, with implications for sustainable water and land management.

Influence of sediment connectivity changes and human pressure on the historical evolution of two Apennine rivers (Northern Italy)

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River morphology and dynamics are controlled by water and sediment fluxes and by the degree of sediment transfer through the fluvial system, defined as sediment connectivity. Structural connectivity regulates the coupling between hillslope sediment sources and channels, thereby influencing sediment supply and channel dynamics. Reduced connectivity, often driven by land use changes and human disturbances, can limit sediment inputs and promote channel incision and narrowing, while direct in-channel interventions may further disrupt sediment fluxes. This study investigates the post-1950s evolution of the Taro River and its main tributary, the Ceno River (Northern Apennines, Italy), focusing on the correlation between channel adjustments and sediment alterations at catchment and reach scales. The specific aims are to: (i) reconstruct and compare the evolutionary trajectories of the two rivers; (ii) assess the impact of hillslope sediment disconnection driven by land use changes; and (iii) evaluate the effects of in-channel human disturbances, including gravel mining and channel works. Channel width and bed-level changes were quantified using multi-temporal orthophotos (1954-2020) and topographic cross-sections. Changes in land use and sediment connectivity were assessed at the catchment scale using multi-temporal land cover maps and the Index of Connectivity, while changes in sediment supply were estimated from the evolution of landslide-prone areas. The influence of human activities was further assessed by mapping gravel mining areas and in-channel works. Results indicate a progressive increase in forest cover, occurring after the 1950s in the Ceno basin and after the 1970s in the Taro basin, accompanied by a reduction in landslide-prone areas. These changes led to a decrease in sediment connectivity and sediment supply to the channel networks. Both rivers experienced significant channel narrowing and bed incision, with reductions in channel width up to 50% and median incision values of -3.3 m in the Taro, and up to 38% and -2.5 m in the Ceno. Despite similar trends, the Taro River exhibited more intense and rapid morphological adjustments, particularly between 1954 and 1976, mainly due to gravel mining and in-channel works, completely absent along the Ceno. Overall, the results highlight the combined role of catchment-scale processes, such as afforestation and hillslope stabilization, and reach-scale human disturbances in controlling sediment connectivity and river evolution. These findings emphasize the importance of considering both basin-wide and local factors when assessing river responses and planning effective management.

Stratigraphy of the Cora maar sedimentary archive: implications for reconstructing the Erciyes eruptive history, paleoseismicity of the Sultansazlığı graben and paleoenvironment of Central Anatolia (Turkey) during the late Pleistocene - Holocene

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The CoraDrill project aims to investigate the sedimentary infill of the Cora maar crater (Central Anatolia Volcanic Province, Turkey) through sediment core drilling. Following an initial presentation of the project at AIQUA 2025, we report here the first results from the March 2026 drilling campaign. Sediment cores were retrieved using a double-barrel drilling system adapted for soft lacustrine deposits. The system combines an outer rotating casing that stabilizes the borehole with an inner liner that recover undisturbed sediment. An additional internal PVC tube and core-catcher were used to reduce deformation during extraction and handling, improving core recovery (~90%) and preserving primary sedimentary structures. The recovered succession comprises ~28.5 m of well-preserved lacustrine sediments overlying remobilised sands and gravels derived from the Cora tuff ring. The lacustrine sequence is characterized by finely laminated, laterally continuous clayey–silty deposits, organic-rich intervals, and interbedded thin primary tephra layers. Preliminary observations highlight the exceptional preservation of sedimentary structures, including possible soft-sediment deformation features such as seismites. These deposits accumulated within a maar structure developed atop of a sediment-filled tectonic depression (gaben), reflects the long-term interplay among volcanism, sedimentation, and tectonics. Laboratory analyses (e.g., sedimentology, palynology, core logging, bulk elemental geochemistry, paleomagnetism, and tephra characterization) will enable high-resolution reconstructions of environmental and climatic variability, as well as their relationships with volcanic and tectonic processes. Tephra layers will also provide a framework for tephrochronological correlations and improve volcanic hazards assessment for Erciyes volcano. These preliminary results identify the Cora maar as a key sedimentary archive in Central Anatolia, preserving one of the longest and most continuous lacustrine records currently known in the region.

Enhanced speleogenesis by CO₂-rich fluids: the role of Quaternary basalts in NW Sardinia (Italy)

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The last Cenozoic volcanic cycle of Sardinia dates back to the Plio-Pleistocene and is characterized by fissural activity with alkaline geochemistry and intraplate affinity, related to extensional tectonics contemporaneous with the formation of the southern Tyrrhenian basin. In the northwestern part of the island, the products of this volcanism (dated at approximately 370 ka) are exclusively represented by Quaternary basaltic lavas that overlie sediments deposited during the Burdigalian–Langhian marine transgression. These alkali basalts display a vesicular texture and occur as sub-horizontal lava flows about 5 m thick, with columnar jointing typical of plateau-type effusive eruptions. They are related to independent eruptive systems that occasionally filled paleodepressions, leading to evident topographic inversion phenomena. In the Torria area (Usini), a NW–SE trending, linear lava flow overlies the marine sedimentary succession that filled Oligo–Miocene structural depressions of western Sardinia (*Rift Sardo Auct.*). Among the various lithofacies identified in this area, the most widespread is attributable to the Mores Formation, consisting of biocalcarenites and bioclastic limestones (often showing well-developed clinofolds) with oyster banks and other bivalves, as well as echinoids. On its western border, this karst plateau is sculptured by the fluviokarst valley of the Rio Mannu, along whose right side, at about 50 m above the riverbed, several small horizontal conduit-like caves open as remnants of an ancient base level at the same elevation. In addition to typical dissolution morphologies, some of these caves exhibit smoothed walls, elliptical cross-sections, solution pockets, dome-like chambers and cupolas, indicating the action of highly aggressive fluids acting over short geological timescales. Field and speleological survey were used to provide a thorough analysis of these underground morphologies. In this study, carbon dioxide originated by the Quaternary regional volcanism is proposed as aggressive fluid involved in the speleogenesis of these karst features.

“Functional” elevation of archeological sea level markers. New data from the archeological site of Nora

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Since the 1960s, the Mediterranean has provided key proxy data for reconstructing sea-level changes over the past millennia. Submerged and semi-submerged archeological remains have been widely used to trace sea-level rise since the Bronze Age, with abundant Hellenistic, Punic and Roman coastal structures helping refine climatic, tectonic, and isostatic interpretations. This approach relies on identifying the original elevation of structures relative to past sea level. However, converting such evidence into reliable sea-level index points remains debated, mainly due to uncertainties in defining such “functional elevation” often estimated using modern analogs that may not reflect past conditions. Here, we present a high-resolution sea-level record from saltmarsh cores near the Punic and Roman city of Nora (southern Sardinia) and compare it with nearby submerged structures to better constrain their relationship with the contemporary sea-level. Integrated lithological, faunal and palynological analysis and a new set of radiocarbon dates allowed to reconstruct the sea-level evolution in the last 4.3 ka BP with a vertical error that did not exceed 0.3 m between 3.4 to ~1.6 ka BP. The comparison between the position of some archeological structures (foundation walls, coastal quarries and the so-called “Schmiedt pier”) with the coeval sea-level position indicate that is very complex to define a general functional elevation for these kinds of structures. Furthermore, our data show that millennial coastline modifications must be also considered. In fact, structures that are now submerged or semi-submerged may have been far from the coast at the time of their construction. For these reasons, our data suggest that sea-level reconstructions based only on archeological markers should be taken with caution because the application of general “functional” values may lead to significant error in the assessment of the past sea-level position.